

SCHOOL LEADERSHIP AND STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT: THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF TEACHER'S BELIEF AMONG FACULTY MEMBERS OF KCAST

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 4

Pages: 376-392

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2968

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14755269

Manuscript Accepted: 01-05-2025

School Leadership and Students' Achievement: The Mediating Effect of Teacher's Belief among Faculty Members of KCAST

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the mediating effect of teachers' beliefs, on the relationship between school leadership, and students' achievement among faculty members of KCAST. Quantitative non-experimental research utilizing descriptive correlational technique and mediation analysis was utilized in this study. The data were gathered from 100 random faculty members who experienced at least 1 to 5 years of service through stratified random sampling. Data gathering was done through face-to-face survey by giving validated questionnaires. Results showed that the level of school leadership, students' achievement, and teachers' belief among faculty members of KCAST were all descriptively at a high level. Results also revealed that the relationship between school leadership and students' achievement, school leadership and teachers' belief, and teachers' belief and students' achievements among faculty members were all highly significant. Moreover, results also revealed that teachers' beliefs partially mediated the relationship between school leadership and students' achievement. This signifies that teachers should not only reflect on their own educational beliefs but also proactively investigate how students perceive and express their interests. Hence, the results offered valuable information that may be utilized by the institution, teachers, and students, as well as future researchers.

Keywords: *teachers' belief, school leadership, students' achievements, faculty members, Philippines*

Introduction

Student achievement is a central focus of educational systems worldwide, as it directly reflects the efficiency of teaching practices, leadership in education, and the comprehensive approach learning environment. High levels of student achievement are associated with improved academic performance, greater opportunities for future success, and the acquisition of skills for lifelong adaptability and personal enrichment. However, schools often face significant struggles in ensuring high levels of student achievement. Challenges include inadequate resources, insufficient teacher training, and a shortage of holistic support systems for students. Addressing these struggles requires a multifaceted approach that includes effective leadership, targeted interventions, and a commitment to creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment (Noguera, 2022).

At Ajloun National University in Jordan, low student achievement is a significant challenge affecting both students and teachers. This issue stems from various causes and encompasses educational, social, cultural, and psychological aspects. Low achievement refers to a student's performance falling below the average level in a subject due to multiple factors. These factors may include issues related to the student, family dynamics, social influences, school management, the learning environment, or teaching practices. As a result, students may experience repeated failures despite having the potential to achieve higher marks. Apart from variations in ability, which are challenging to manage, students possess distinct learning styles that can impact their academic performance (Sternberg, 2017).

In the Philippines, according to a study conducted by the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), everyone has the potential to succeed both academically and in life. However, students worldwide often encounter failure in school due to a range of complex factors. These include insufficient support and encouragement from teachers and school leaders, a lack of motivation to thrive in academic settings, and challenges related to demographic, socioeconomic, and cultural barriers. Additionally, their academic performance may not always be accurately assessed. This issue is further exacerbated by the lack of motivation among educators and leaders to prioritize and address student achievement (Borman, 2019).

As such, this is indeed an alarming phenomenon nowadays and students are having problems regarding their academic achievements towards school leadership and teachers' performance. With these important issues at hand, the researcher embarks and initiates this study to confirm whether there is the researcher felt it is necessary to conduct this research to explore how teachers' beliefs mediate the connection between school leadership and student achievements. Further, the study could broaden the scope of whether teachers' belief has application in school leadership towards the students' achievements among teachers, school heads, and students. The importance this research demonstrates the impact that style of leadership may have a relationship towards students' achievements in teachers' beliefs. Moreover, it is socially relevant as it can result in more effective instructional practices and more positive learning environments that produce better academic outcomes for students' achievements.

In connection, the researcher had not come across a study in the Philippines, particularly in the locality, that covered all of the said variables. There have been studies such as those of Kennedy (2018), entitled "Leadership and Learning are Indispensable to each other" Trust Matters: Leadership for Successful Schools", and Herrera et al. (2019) entitled "Teacher's Beliefs and Practices: their effects on students achievements in a school setting," which focused on the teacher's belief but not focused on the significant relationship with the school leadership in students achievements, the respondents are not college education students and where not conducted during the

new learning modality.

The primary purpose of this study was to explore how teachers' beliefs mediate the relationship between school leadership and students' academic achievements. It aimed to provide insight into how classroom practices and lesson planning evolve under different leadership styles. The research was designed to give a thorough understanding of the correlation between the measured variables and the constructed variables. The copies of the study were disseminated to various research conferences and concerned agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to examine the mediating effect of teachers' beliefs on the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements. To be specific, this study sought answers to the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of school leadership in terms of:
 - 1.1. instructional leadership;
 - 1.2. transformational leadership; and
 - 1.3. transactional leadership.
2. To determine the level of student's achievements in terms of:
 - 2.1. concentrations;
 - 2.2. motivation; and
 - 2.3. engagement.
3. To determine the level of teacher's belief in terms of:
 - 3.1. commitments to school mission;
 - 3.2. teacher professional commitment; and
 - 3.3. collective teachers' efficacy.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. school leadership and students' achievement in teachers' belief;
 - 4.2. teachers' beliefs and students' achievement; and
 - 4.3. school leadership and students' achievements.
5. To determine the mediating effect of teacher's belief on the school leadership towards student's achievements.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between school leadership and students' achievement specifically by examining the role of teachers' beliefs as a mediating factor. Quantitative research is an empirical approach that seeks to test objective theories by examining relationships among variables. In this type of research, variables are typically measured using instruments, leading to numerical data that can be analyzed using statistical methods and structured tools like questionnaires. The data collected is often presented in tabular form, and the findings tend to be conclusive and descriptive, serving as a basis for recommending specific courses of action (Habib, 2021)

This study was quantitative, measuring variables to test correlations. It focused on understanding how school leadership and students' achievement mediate teachers' beliefs, collecting data such as ratings or survey responses from teachers who had experienced the leadership. This data was then analyzed to see if there were any significant patterns or relationships between the school leadership and students' achievement specifically as the role of teachers' belief as a mediating factor.

A correlational research approach is a quantitative research method used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. In scientific research, this method is non-experimental, used to assess the relationship between two or more variables, where changes in one variable are associated with changes in another, and focuses on several key aspects. It is essential to note that despite its limitations, correlational is valuable for making predictions (Price et al., 2014)

The correlational research design was considered because this study aimed to explore the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. In this case, examine the relationships between school leadership, teachers' beliefs, and student achievement without changing or controlling any of these factors. It will look at how leadership practices are connected to teachers' beliefs, and how those beliefs relate to students' achievement. This design is often used when the researcher wants to examine the two variables to determine their statistical association with little to no effort on the part of the researcher to control the other variables.

The descriptive-correlational research approach is a quantitative research method employed to collect data and analyze its association with specific phenomena. In scientific research, this method involves gathering information without intervening or making alternations to the study subjects. Descriptive research within the context focuses on observing and documenting behaviors and characteristics of both the phenomenon being studied and the participants involved. It is essential to note that descriptive research is not designed for making predictions or establishing causation: rather its primary aim is to identify, describe, and potentially establish correlations among

variables of interest (Tremmer, 2023).

The descriptive-correlational design was considered because this study aimed to explore the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. A descriptive correlational design involved collecting data on the variables of interest and analyzing them using correlation statistics to identify any relationship between the variables. This design was often used when the researcher wanted to examine the natural occurrence of variables in a specific population and explore the association between them.

The mediation analysis is a statistical used to understand how an independent variable (IV) influences a dependent variable (DV) through a third variable, Known as the mediator. The goal of mediation analysis was to determine whether the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable occurs indirectly through the mediator, which helps clarify the pathway of the relationship between variables. Mediation analysis involves the inclusion of a third variable to this $X \rightarrow Y$ relation. The third variable M is a link between X and Y whereby X causes the mediator, M , and causes Y , so $X + M \rightarrow Y$ (MacKinnon et al., 2007).

In this study, the researcher used mediation analysis where the independent variable here was school leadership, the dependent variable was students' achievement, and the mediating variable was teachers' beliefs. In this study, the researcher determined the strength and significance of the mediation effect. This allows for a deeper understanding of the processes through which leadership indirectly influences student achievement, providing insights into how fostering positive teacher beliefs through strong leadership can improve educational outcomes. Therefore a correlational design would have been appropriate for this study because it would have allowed the researcher to describe variables and identify any correlation between them without manipulating the variables in any way.

Respondents

The participants in this study included the faculty members of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is all about the school leadership and student's achievements, the mediating effects of teacher's beliefs, since the study purpose involves teachers' beliefs and students' achievements, it would be fitting and valid to include faculty members in the local college of Kapalong. Moreover, to ensure an accurate distribution of samples, the researchers utilized stratified random sampling, specifically proportional allocation, using Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. Table 1 shows the distribution of the population of this study.

In a process known as stratified random sampling, a random sample is chosen from each stratum after the population has been divided into smaller groups or strata based on relevant factors like age, gender, or teaching ability. To maximize the generalizability of the results, stratified random sampling can assist ensure that the sample is adequate for each subgroup and that it is representative of the population as a whole. The population must be characterized, though, and the pertinent criteria for stratification must be known to use this strategy (Etikan & Bala, 2017). The stratified random sampling is particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents of this research will be randomly selected based on the strata, which are in this case, faculty members of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology.

To compute the sample, the researcher would gather first the data on the population of respondents by writing a formal request letter to the college president, requesting access to the population of respondents. After gathering the data, the researcher would relay this information to her statistician for the computation of the study sample. Consequently, the statistician would give the following computed data indicating the sample appropriate for the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Position</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Casual Instructors	16	12	12%
Part-time Instructors	43	32	32%
Full-time Instructors	74	56	56%
Total	133	100	84.03%

The study was conducted among faculty members with at least 1 to 5 years of service in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The institution has a total of 133 faculty members, consisting of 16 casual instructors 43 part-time instructors, and 74 full-time instructors. Further, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician which included 12 out of 16 casual instructors and staff, 32 out of 43 part-time instructors, and 56 out of 74 full-time instructors both male and female of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Instrument

The researcher adapted three downloadable questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instrument for school leadership is adapted from the study of Ross (2006), entitled "School Leadership Inventory Canadian Journal of Education questionnaire". Also, the instrument for the student's achievement is adapted from the study of Sbrocco (2009), which is the "Student Academic Engagement and the academic achievement scale". Lastly, the instrument for teachers' belief is adapted from the study of Kapat (2022), entitled "The Collective Teacher Efficacy Behaviours Scale".

The teacher's belief questionnaire has three indicators: commitment to school mission with five items, teachers' professional

commitment with five items, and collective teachers' efficacy with five items. The school leadership questionnaires have three indicators: transformational leadership with five items, instructional leadership with five items, and transactional leadership with five items. The student achievement questionnaires have three indicators: concentration with five items, motivation with five items, and engagement with five items.

An instrument that was used in survey research to quantify respondents' views regarding a particular topic is the Likert Scale. The main advantage of employing a Likert Scale over a simple yes/no question type is that it provides more detailed information about people's attitudes regarding a subject. Likert Scale questions are single-choice, closed-ended questions. Researchers can evaluate various degrees of agreement, relevance, quality, and other variables by utilizing a Likert Scale (Roxana, 2021). Both questionnaires will be content validated by the panel of experts. For each item, the respondents were requested to describe their response based on the five-point Likert Scale anchored at (5) Always, (4) Oftentimes, (3) Sometimes, (2) Seldom, and (1) Never.

Procedure

In gathering the data the researcher would follow these steps to collect the necessary data for the study.

Crafting and Validation of the Survey Questionnaires. The researcher crafted the questionnaires, which were modified and contextualized for each item to ensure their appropriateness for the respondents. These questionnaires were also subjected to expert validation, which was facilitated by the panel of examiners.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher sought permission from the research panel to allow the dissemination of the questionnaires to the participants.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Upon the approval of the conduct of the study, the researcher made a letter of consent addressed to the local college in the Municipality of Kapalong. The researcher also distributed the research instrument and personally oriented the respondents on how to answer the questionnaires.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. After the respondents completely answered all the test questionnaires, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires for encoding and used Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. The researcher then endorsed the results to the statistician for computation, tabulation, and analysis with utmost confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of the data and testing the hypotheses at the alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of mediating effect of teachers' beliefs, school leadership, and students' achievements towards success among students and faculty members of KCAST.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements toward success, school leadership and teachers' belief, and students' achievements toward success and teachers' belief.

Structural Equation Modelling (Mediation Analysis). This was used to analyze the mediation of the mediating variable on the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements towards success.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were all the faculty members of KCAST the local college in the municipality of Kapalong Davao del Norte. In this case, the researcher made sure that the respondents' safety, rights, and reliance on the researcher, as well as the study's goals, would be treated with fairness and righteous action.

Furthermore, when conducting research with humans as respondents, the researcher must adhere to the highest ethical standards. The primary goal of this quantitative investigation is to ensure that the study was ethically sound to protect the human respondent's comfort. The researcher discussed how the study adhered to the following Denzin and Lincoln's (2011) guidelines, which focused on three key principles: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity, and confidentiality, as well as conflict of interest.

Informed Consent. It is the first essential ethical to take into account. The obligations, the intended use of the data, and any potential consequences must be adequately disclosed to the respondents. The respondents must provide their explicit, active, and written consent to participate in the study. They must also state that they are aware of their right to access their information and that they are free to change their minds at any time. An agreement between the researcher and the respondents may be taken into account during the process of obtaining informed permission (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this case, the researcher includes an informed consent question in a printed survey form, asking the respondents of the study if they are still willing to participate despite the risks. When the respondents are unsure about the agreement, they may choose to decline. Making informed decisions and participating in the study voluntarily are strongly encouraged. The researcher ensures that all the respondents in the study are enthusiastic about it and eager to participate. It is critical to base their responses on the available surveys while gathering data.

During the informed consent process, the respondents were oriented on the following rights that they have. The respondents were informed that they had the right to terminate participation without any need for explanation. They also have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. Another right is that they have the entitlement to ask questions about the study. Lastly, they also have the right to be informed of the study results after this research is accomplished.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. The respondents' information must always be kept confidential or hidden, and promises have to go further than just keeping their names private to include refraining from using identity remarks and material. Anonymity and secrecy are steps in safeguarding people from possible harm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

There is a possible risk of harm in terms of social liabilities when the data is carefully disclosed to others. As such, data of the study shall be maintained private and secured to avoid this incident from happening. The researcher made sure to emphasize to the respondents that their safety, identity, and personal information would be protected and that their participation in the study would be important to them. To create an error-free collection, the researcher removes identities from the data. A clean data collection does not contain any data that could be used to identify the respondents, such as names or addresses (such identifying data could be stored in separate, secure files elsewhere). Data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the study is accomplished.

Conflict of Interest. Present connections or prior actions of the researcher may result in a conflict of interest, which needs to be reported transparently in an ethical committee application so that the committee may advise on how to address the conflict (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018). However, the study's research asserts that the research was carried out in the absence of any business or financial ties that may be interpreted as a possible conflict of interest.

This viewpoint holds the research activities were unaffected by outside factors because the respondents were the teachers, and the researcher had no competing interest in the study. Conflict of interest only arises when the researcher has the power to use coercive methods to force respondents to participate, such as threats of termination of benefits, blackmail, or other forms of punishment (e.g., principals' threatening to fire teachers or teachers' threatening to fail their students if they do not respond to the survey).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and results on the relationship between school leadership and students' achievement. Also, this chapter presents the mediating effect of the teachers' beliefs on the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Data analyses and interpretations of the data were done parallel to the research objectives.

Level of School Leadership in Terms of Transformational Leadership

The level of school leadership was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of transformational leadership. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 2 is the level of school leadership in terms of transformational leadership with a corresponding overall mean of 4.60 which is interpreted as very high. This indicates that the indicator of transformational leadership under the variable school leadership is always manifested. Moreover, it can be observed from the data that item no. 2 - Promoting an atmosphere of caring and trust among staff, students, and teachers, has the highest mean 4.74 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested. On the other hand, item no. 4 - Changing own practices in light of new understanding for the students and teachers, has the lowest mean rating 4.28 which is descriptively very high. This only means that the item is always manifested.

Table 2. *Level of School Leadership in Terms of Transformational Leadership*

<i>Transformational Leadership</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Providing moral support by making the students and teachers feel appreciated and valued	4.65	Very High
2. Promoting an atmosphere of caring and trust among staff, students and teachers	4.74	Very High
3. Setting a respectful tone for interaction with teachers and students	4.59	Very High
4. Changing own practices in light of new understanding for the students and teachers	4.28	Very High
5. Modelling problem-solving techniques that I can use in my work	4.73	Very High
Overall	4.60	Very High

Level of School Leadership in Terms of Instructional Leadership

The level of school leadership was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, of instructional leadership. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 3 is the level of school leadership in terms of instructional leadership with a corresponding overall mean of 4.69 which is interpreted as very high. This indicates that the indicator instructional leadership under the variable school leadership is always manifested.

Moreover, the data reveals that item no. 1 - Encouraging teachers to use instructional materials freely, has the highest mean 4.88 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested. On the other hand, item no. 4 - Visiting classes regularly to observe teaching and learning, has the lowest mean rating 4.19 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Table 3. *Level of School Leadership in Terms of Instructional Leadership*

<i>Instructional Leadership</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Encouraging teachers to use instructional materials freely	4.88	Very High
2. Organizing and delivering the instructional materials to teachers	4.83	Very High
3. Recommending resources in areas in which teachers need	4.71	Very High
4. Visiting classes regularly to observe teaching and learning	4.19	High
5. Attending co-curricular activities of the school	4.86	Very High
Overall	4.69	Very High

Level of School Leadership in Terms of Transactional Leadership

The level of school leadership of teachers in higher education was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of transactional leadership. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 4 is the level of school leadership in terms of transactional leadership with a corresponding overall mean of 4.15 which is interpreted as high. This indicates that the indicator of transactional leadership under the variable school leadership is oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of School Leadership in Terms of Transactional Leadership*

<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Giving positive feedback for the good efforts of their teachers and students	4.88	Very High
2. Making clear what the students can expect when they perform well	4.83	Very High
3. Providing rewards contingent on staff performance	4.71	Very High
4. Monitoring the performance of the teachers and keeping track of their mistakes	4.19	High
5. Taking action before problems are chronic	4.86	Very High
Overall	4.69	Very High

Moreover, the data reveals that item no.3 - Visiting classes regularly to observe teaching and learning, has the highest mean 4.51 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested.

On the other hand, item no. 5 - Taking actions before problems are chronic, has the lowest mean rating 3.87 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Summary on the Level of School Leadership

The summary on the level of school leadership is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Reflected in Table 5 is the summary of the level of school leadership of faculty members with a corresponding overall mean of 4.48 which is interpreted as very high.

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of School Leadership*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Transformational Leadership	4.60	Very High
Instructional Leadership	4.69	Very High
Transactional Leadership	4.15	High
Overall	4.48	Very High

It can be observed in the table that the indicator instructional leadership, got the highest mean of 4.69 which is descriptively interpreted as very high, while the indicator transactional leadership, got the lowest mean score of 4.15 which is descriptively interpreted as high.

Thus, it can be observed in the table that the indicators instructional leadership is descriptively very high and transactional leadership is descriptively high, the indicator transactional leadership has a lower mean score compared to the indicator instructional leadership. This signifies that the summary of the level of teachers in higher education is always manifested.

Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Concentration

The level of students' achievement was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator concentration. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 6 is the level of students' achievement in terms of concentration with a corresponding overall mean of 4.42 which is interpreted as very high. This indicates that the indicator concentration under the variable students' achievement is always manifested.

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that the item no. 3 - Fostering a creative and engaging learning environment for them to improve their competencies in every subject, has the highest mean of 4.55 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested.

On the other hand, item no. 1 - Making my students ready in all my subjects, has the lowest mean rating 4.30 which is descriptively very high. This only means that the item is always manifested.

Table 6. *Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Concentration*

<i>Concentration</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Making my students ready in all my subjects	4.30	Very High
2. Using technology and multimedia tools to help my students' concentration in the classroom	4.53	Very High
3. Fostering a creative and engaging learning environment for them to improve their competencies in every subject	4.55	Very High
4. Taking risks in the classroom without feeling embarrassed	4.41	Very High
5. Connecting with my students on a personal level, showing an interest in their well-being and success	4.33	Very High
Overall	4.42	Very High

Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Motivation

The level of students' achievement was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of motivation. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 7 is the level of students' achievement in terms of motivation with a corresponding overall mean of 4.16 which is interpreted as high. This indicates that the indicator motivation under the variable students' achievement is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. *Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Motivation*

<i>Motivation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Motivating my students to give their best effort in making their tasks and performances	4.40	Very High
2. Motivating my students through inspiring teaching every day	3.89	High
3. Making positive comments about the student's abilities to learn	4.46	Very High
4. Viewing my students as an important part of the classroom	4.09	High
5. Encouraging my students in active participation and critical thinking	3.95	High
Overall	4.16	High

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that the item no. 3 - Motivating my students to give their best effort in making their tasks and performances, has the highest mean 4.88 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested. On the other hand, item no. 2 - Motivating my students through inspiring teaching every day, has the lowest mean rating 3.89 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Engagement

The level of students' achievement was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of engagement. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 8 is the level of students' achievement in terms of engagement with a corresponding overall mean of 4.27 which is interpreted as very high. This indicates that the indicator engagement under the variable students' achievement is always manifested.

Table 8. *Level of Students' Achievement in Terms of Engagement*

<i>Engagement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Making teaching attractive by showing how theory is implemented in the real world	4.38	Very High
2. Taking risks in classroom learning activities	4.07	High
3. Engaging my students in participating in extracurricular activities (e.g. organizations, campus publications, student associations, clubs and societies, sports, etc.)	4.29	Very High
4. Using various cultural activities in the lessons, like experimentation, case studies, live examples, etc.	4.28	Very High
5. Structuring with routines and procedures inside the classroom	4.33	Very High
Overall	4.27	Very High

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that item no. 1 - Making teaching attractive by showing how theory is implemented in the real world, has the highest mean 4.38 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested.

On the other hand, item no. 2 - Taking risks in classroom learning activities, has the lowest mean rating 4.07 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Summary on the Level of Students' Achievement

The summary on the level of students' achievement was presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Reflected in Table 9 is the summary on the level of students' achievement of faculty members with a corresponding overall mean of 4.28 which is interpreted as very high.

It can be observed in the table that the indicator Concentration, got the highest mean of 4.42 which is descriptively interpreted as very high, while the indicator Motivation, got the lowest mean score of 4.16 which is descriptively interpreted as high. Thus, it can be

observed in the table that the indicator concentration is descriptively interpreted as very high and motivation is descriptively high, the indicator motivation has a lower mean score compared to the indicator concentration. This signifies that the summary on the level of students' achievement of faculty members is always manifested.

Table 9. Summary on the Level of Students' Achievement

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Concentration	4.42	Very High
Motivation	4.16	Very High
Engagement	4.27	High
Overall	4.28	Very High

Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Commitments to School Mission

The level of teachers' belief was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of commitment to school mission. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 10 is the level of teachers' belief in terms of commitments to the school mission with a corresponding overall mean of 3.83 which is interpreted as high. This indicates that the indicator commitments to school mission under the variable teachers' beliefs are oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that item no. 1 - Encouraging to develop action plans for improving own professional growth, has the highest mean 4.21 which is descriptively high. This signifies that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Table 10. Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Commitments to School Mission

<i>Commitments to School Mission</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Encouraging to develop action plans for improving own professional growth	4.21	High
2. Having the information they need to participate in school decision-making	3.51	High
3. Working toward consensus in determining which initiatives can be implemented	3.41	High
4. Willing to go the extra mile to ensure that my students are achieving the mission's educational objectives	3.99	High
5. Having an atmosphere of caring and trust among staff at this school	4.04	High
Overall	3.83	High

On the other hand, the item no. 3 - Working toward consensus in determining which initiatives can be implemented, has the lowest mean rating 3.41 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Teacher Professional Commitment

The level of teachers' belief of teachers in higher education was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of teacher professional commitment. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 11 is the level of teachers' belief in terms of teacher professional commitment with a corresponding overall mean of 4.13 which is interpreted as high. This indicates that the indicator of teacher professional commitment under the variable teachers' belief is oftentimes manifested.

Table 11. Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Teacher Professional Commitment

<i>Teacher Professional Commitment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Helping new teachers to learn what is expected of teachers in this school	4.54	Very High
2. Learning new teaching techniques that can get help in this school	3.73	High
3. Utilizing effective teaching strategies such as active learning, group discussion, and multimedia resources	4.57	Very High
4. Feeling obliged to mediate among the rival groups of the students	4.02	High
5. Having a dynamic relationship with students and colleagues	3.79	High
Overall	3.13	High

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that the item no. 3 - Utilizing effective teaching strategies such as active learning, group discussion, and multimedia resources, has the highest mean 4.57 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested.

On the other hand, item no. 2 - Learning new teaching technique, that can get help in this school, has the lowest mean rating of 3.73 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Collective Teachers' Efficacy

The level of teachers' belief was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of collective teachers' efficacy. The responses of the respondents on the indicator are presented and analyzed below. Reflected in Table 12 is the level of teachers' belief

in terms of collective teachers' efficacy with a corresponding overall mean of 4.35 which is interpreted as very high. This indicates that the indicator of collective teachers' efficacy under the variable teachers' belief is always manifested.

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that item no. 1 - Expressing opinions in decisions concerning the entire school, has the highest mean 4.60 which is descriptively very high. This signifies that the item is always manifested.

On the other hand, item no. 2 - Organizing various outdoor activities (trips, social events, etc.) with our colleagues, has the lowest mean rating 3.72 which is descriptively high. This only means that the item is oftentimes manifested.

Table 12. Level of Teachers' Belief in Terms of Collective Teachers' Efficacy

<i>Collective Teachers' Efficacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Expressing opinions in decisions concerning the entire school	4.60	Very High
2. Organizing various outdoor activities (trips, social events, etc.) with our colleagues	3.72	High
3. Asking for feedback from teacher colleagues at school in improving education	4.25	Very High
4. Assuring that I can adapt and modify my teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of my students	4.67	Very High
5. Believing that the effectiveness of my professional development and collective learning experiences will enhance student outcomes	4.53	Very High
Overall	4.37	Very High

Summary on the Level of Teachers' Belief

The summary on the level of teachers' beliefs was presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Reflected in Table 13 is the summary on the level of teachers' belief of faculty members with a corresponding overall mean of 4.10 which is interpreted as high.

It can be observed in the table that the indicator Collective Teachers' efficacy, got the highest mean of 4.35 which is descriptively interpreted as very high, while the indicator commitment to school mission, got the lowest mean score of 3.83 which is descriptively interpreted as high.

Thus, it can be observed in the table that the indicators of collective teachers' efficacy are descriptively very high and commitment to school mission is descriptively high, the indicator commitment to school mission has a lower mean score compared to the indicator commitments to school mission. This signifies that the summary on the level of teachers' belief of faculty members in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology is oftentimes manifested.

Table 13. Summary on the Level of Teachers' Belief

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Commitments to School Mission	3.83	High
Teacher Professional Commitment	4.13	High
Collective Teachers' Efficacy	4.35	Very High
Overall	4.10	High

Significant Relationship between School Leadership and Students Achievement

Table 14 presents the result of the significant relationship between school leadership and students' achievements, $r=.244$, $p<.001$. Since the probability value ($p<.001$) is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance set in the study, as a result, the null hypothesis is rejected in this context. This stipulates that there is a significant relationship between student's achievements and school leadership.

Table 14. Significant Relationship between Student Achievement and School Leadership

<i>Variables Correlated</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision $\alpha = 0.05$</i>
Student's Achievement	4.28	.244	<.001	Ho Rejected
School Leadership	4.48			

Significant Relationship Between Student's Achievement and Teacher Belief

Presented in Table 15, the relationship between student achievement and teacher belief with an overall r-value of .148 and an equivalent value of $p<.041$ which is less than the 0.05 level of significance set in this study.

As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected in this context. This stipulates that there is a significant relationship between student achievement and teacher belief.

Mediation Analysis

The Preacher and Hayes, mediation analysis approach, is utilized in this study to determine if a teacher's belief mediates the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship between Students' Achievement and Teachers' Belief*

<i>Variables Correlated</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision $\alpha = 0.05$</i>
Student's Achievement	4.28			
		.148	<.001	Ho Rejected
Teachers Belief	4.11			

Significant Relationship between Teachers' Belief and School Leadership

Table 16 presents the result of the significant relationship between school leadership and teachers' beliefs, $r=.207$, $p<.001$. Since the probability value ($p<.001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance set in the study, as a result, the null hypothesis is rejected in this context. This stipulates that there is a significant relationship between teacher's beliefs and school leadership.

It is a Structural Equation Modelling (Mediation Analysis) that is used to analyze the mediation of the mediating variable on the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements. It consists of two steps that reflect the recommendation for mediation analysis. In step 1, the indirect effect is tested for significance. If this effect is significant, we can conclude that there is a mediation.

Table 16. *Significant Relationship between School Leadership and Teachers' Belief*

<i>Variables Correlated</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision $\alpha = 0.05$</i>
Teachers Belief	4.11			
		.207	<.041	Ho Rejected
School Leadership	4.48			

Step 2 involves defining the type of effect and mediation, which is classified into partial and full mediation.

Full mediation is achieved if the direct effect is not significant and the indirect effect is significant. It means that only the indirect effect via the mediator exists. On the other hand, partial mediation happens when the direct effect is significant. Tables 17, 18, and 19 present the summary of the mediation analysis outcome.

Table 17. *Mediation Analysis (Indirect Effect)*

	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
					<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
IV \rightarrow MV \rightarrow DV	0.086	0.033	2.606	<.009	0.153	0.020

Presented in Table 17 the indirect effect of school leadership (IV) on students' achievement (DV) and teachers' belief (MV) showed [$\beta=0.086$, $SE=0.033$, 95% CI (0.153, 0.020)], and it indicates that the confidence interval does not include zero. At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, $p<.009$. This announces that the teacher's belief (MV) mediates the relationship between the school leadership (IV) and student's achievement (DV).

Table 18. *Mediation Analysis (Direct Effect)*

	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
					<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
IV \rightarrow DV	0.444	0.150	2.965	<.003	0.150	0.737

In addition, Table 18 shows the direct effect of school leadership (IV) on student achievement (DV). Based on the result, the direct effect of school leadership and student achievement is significant [$\beta=0.444$, $SE=0.150$, 95% CI (0.150, 0.737)]. Since the confidence interval in the direct effect does not include zero, it indicates that the direct effect of the school leadership and student achievement is significant. It also revealed that school leadership significantly influenced student's achievement, ($\beta=0.444$, $p<.003$). Also, based on the result, school leadership significantly influences the student's achievement even without the presence of the teacher's belief.

Table 19. *Mediation Analysis (Total Effect)*

	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z - value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
					<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
IV \rightarrow DV	.377	.150	2.519	<.012	.084	.671

It can be observed in Table 19 the total effect of school leadership (IV) on student achievement (DV). The result yielded a beta of 0.377 which is from the sum of each beta in Tables 17 and 18, and a standard error (SE) of 0.044 with $p<.012$ or significant. Also, reflected in the table that the total effect is positive since the 95% confidence interval is [0.084, 0.671], which does not include zero. Also, as shown in the results, it could be inferred that for every unit increase in the student's achievement will entice a 0.377 increase in the teacher's belief. The result stipulates that student achievement is significantly influencing school leadership.

In addition to the result of the study, Figure 1 shows the path estimates between School Leadership and Students' Achievement (Path c), School Leadership and Teachers' Belief (Path a), and Teachers' Belief and Figure 3 shows the path estimates between School

Leadership and Students (Path b). It revealed that school leadership significantly influenced student achievement, $\beta=0.44$, $p<.009$. Also, school leadership significantly affected teachers' beliefs, $\beta=0.24$, $p<.012$. Lastly, teachers' belief is found to be a significant predictor of students' achievement, $\beta=0.28$, $p<.003$.

Figure 1. Path Analysis Showing the Variables of the Study

These results suggested the relationship between school leadership and students' achievement was partially mediated by the indirect pathway through teachers' belief, a claim that was also supported in Table 21 by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

Further, the extent of school leadership should not be confined or limited. Teachers should look into other factors that are affecting the students' achievement of a student and not just the school leadership. Perhaps, teachers should also consider the engagement of students specifically students' concentration and motivation, as it partially mediates or significantly affects the relationship of school leadership and students' achievement.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn in answer to the question raised in the previous chapter.

Faculty members demonstrate a high sense of school leadership. This reveals that the respondents have given importance and significant value to school leadership and have developed a high sense of ability to learn leadership styles.

Subsequently, the respondents demonstrate an overall high level of student achievement. This signifies the positive perception of the students in terms of concentration, motivation, and engagement. Also, it demonstrates a sense of understanding and the capacity on the part of respondents to deal with and attain learning achievements.

Also, the respondents demonstrate a high sense of teachers' beliefs. This indicates that the teachers have gained self-efficacy and commitment in their ability to deal with leadership and achievement.

Moreover, there is a significant relationship among the three variables: school leadership and students' achievement; school leadership and teachers' belief; and teachers' belief and students' achievement, which were tested in this study and in which the null hypothesis was rejected.

On top of that, the mediation analysis reveals that the mediating variable which is the teachers' belief has partially mediated or significantly affected the relationship between the independent variable which is the school leadership, and the dependent variable which is the students' achievement. Therefore, teachers should not just have an interest in leadership but also have a positive conception to have a strong perception of learning.

Finally, the results of this study are consistent with McClelland's (1961) achievement motivation theory, which claims that students who have concentration, motivation, and engagement are more likely to be successful in achieving school success. This theory demonstrates that the association between students' achievements and school leadership would result in a significantly positive relationship. Besides, the students boost their interest if they are aware of what they are learning.

Based on the findings, teachers' beliefs, school leadership, and students' achievement revealed high results; therefore, it is recommended that students focus on the enhancement of their academic achievement, competence development, and self-concept. Also, students may boost their motivation and concentration to get good learning achievements.

Results showed that the faculty members demonstrate a high sense of school leadership. This implies that there is a significant relationship between school leadership associated with teachers' beliefs and students' achievement. With that, leaders may focus on the development of their high sense of strategies, which contributes to leadership and achievement. To increase their interest in school success, leaders may be able to develop their strategies and leadership.

Also, results showed that the faculty members demonstrate an overall high level of student achievement. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the students' achievement associated with teachers' beliefs and school leadership. With that, students may focus on their aspirations in order to improve their learning achievements, as it has been found that this could impact concentration and their motivation.

Moreover, results showed that the faculty members demonstrate a high sense of teachers' belief. This indicates that the teachers have gained self-fulfillment and honesty in their ability to deal with teacher professional commitment, it has been found that there is a significant relationship between teachers' beliefs as associated with school leadership and students' achievement. With that, teachers may focus on working with their efficacy, as it has been found that this could help enhance leadership and teachers' beliefs.

Students may also consider building their confidence which can significantly influence their concentration and engagement, as it also significantly impacts their motivation in learning achievements.

The teacher may think about motivational strategies that aim to improve their sense of connection and confidence in dealing with their students. This will help them not only think about how motivated they are to develop their students' concentration, and motivation and openly engage in learning achievements.

Also, the results of this study show that teachers' belief significantly mediates the relationship between school leadership and students' achievements. Because of this, the institution may want to think of ways to help teachers improve their ability to connect with their selves and encourage them to develop their strategies in dealing students achievement.

Furthermore, future researchers are urged to examine other factors that might completely mediate the association between school leadership and students' achievement. Additionally, they might look at this study utilizing a large-scale population.

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